

Validation of the Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Scale towards Maghrebi immigrants in a Spanish sample*

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The present study describes the validation and adaptation of the *Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Scale* (SBPM) towards Maghrebis in the Spanish context and examines its relationship with other psychosocial variables. A Spanish sample of 797 participants from Madrid was used. The analyses were performed using Confirmatory Factor Analysis, mainly considering the statistical indexes Comparative Fit Index, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation, and Pearson Correlation. External validity of the scale was tested using variables such as Social Dominance Orientation (SDO), Empathic Concern, Warmth and Competence, and Intergroup Contact with Maghrebis. Results indicated that the SBPM scale showed adequate psychometric properties. The SBPM scale was found to correlate positively with SDO, while correlating

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Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee for Research with Human Beings (CEISH) of Valencia International University. The Committee confirmed that the research met ethical standards, as it focused solely on participants' attitudes and general opinions, without experimental procedures. Participation was voluntary and based on informed consent, collected via a written form prior to survey access. The sample did not include patients, and all data were anonymized and used exclusively for academic purposes.

* This is an early electronic version of the manuscript that has been accepted for publication in *Psihologija* journal but has not yet been technically prepared for publication. Please note that this is not the final version of the paper as it has yet to be technically prepared for publication and minor changes to the text are possible before the final print. The final version of the article can be subjected to minor changes after proof reading and before final print. Please cite as: Guido, J. I., Etchezahar, E., Albalá Genol, M. Á., & Ungaretti, J. (2025). Validation of the Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Scale towards Maghrebi immigrants in a Spanish sample. *Psihologija*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.2298/PSI231207038G>

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negatively with the rest of the variables. Therefore, the results show that the SBPM scale can be used as a reliable measure to assess prejudiced attitudes towards Maghrebi immigrants in Spain. The implications of the psychosocial variables studied are discussed to promote the reduction of prejudice towards Maghrebi immigrants in the Spanish context.

Keywords: Prejudice; Stereotypes; Social Dominance Orientation; Migrants; Scale

Highlights:

- The Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Scale towards Maghrebi immigrants was validated in Spain.
- Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) supported a two-factor model for the SBPS.
- Pearson's Correlation Index showed significant associations with all psychosocial variables analyzed.

The present study is dedicated to the adaptation and validation of the *Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Scale* (SBPS) developed by Pettigrew and Meertens (1995) to the Spanish context, focusing specifically on attitudes towards Maghrebi immigrants. The SBPS was originally designed to measure two different forms of prejudice: *subtle*, which is indirect and ostensibly more socially acceptable; and *blatant*, which is direct and openly hostile. This scale has been extensively validated in several international contexts (Arancibia Martini et al., 2016; Etchezahar et al., 2023; Palacio et al., 2020), underscoring its utility and relevance in capturing nuanced forms of prejudice in different settings.

In recent decades, many social scientists have focused on studying the psychosocial factors involved in the increasing migratory movements towards Spain (Martínez & Martínez García, 2018). Many studies have shown that negative attitudes and stereotypes towards immigrants have a significant impact on their wellbeing (Berry & Hou, 2017; Szaflarski & Bauldry, 2019). According to the National Institute of Statistics (2021), the migrant population has increased by 2% in 2021 compared to the previous year. This report highlights that of all the immigrant populations in Spain, the Moroccan community is the most numerous and represents the majority of immigrants in the country. Moreover, due to the sociopolitical conflicts in the Maghreb region in North Africa (Morocco, Algeria, Libya, Mauritania, and Tunisia) and the closeness to the Iberian Peninsula, a large part of the population of these countries decides to migrate to Spain in pursuit of a better quality of life. In many cases, the migrants take an enormous risk crossing the Mediterranean Sea in very dangerous conditions to reach the Spanish coast (Spanish Commission of Refugee Aid, 2021). In this sense, the migratory flows to Spain are increasing year after year, and the Spanish society is becoming more intercultural, with inhabitants of different ethnicities and cultures. As a result, there are many racist and xenophobic attitudes among the

native population towards different groups of immigrants (Bustos et al., 2019). Despite the significant contribution that immigrants make to the host country, the social exclusion that they face seems inevitable (Esses, 2021).

The Maghrebi community in Spain is one of the minority groups that suffer the most prejudice and discrimination from the Spanish population in all areas of daily life (education, work, social, etc.; Albalá Genol et al., 2021). Thus, social exclusion and inequality are two determining aspects used to comprehend the current situation of the Maghrebi population in Spain. Given the growing levels of interculturalism that Spain is currently experiencing, it is important to focus on the understanding of the psychological factors that are involved in the negative attitudes towards immigrants and particularly the Maghrebi community, since they are one of the most affected groups (Human Rights Association of Andalucía, 2021).

From a psychosocial perspective, prejudice was defined by Allport (1954) as an “antipathy based upon a faulty and inflexible generalization that could be felt or expressed directed toward a group as a whole, or toward an individual as a member of that group” (p. 9). Although explicit expressions of prejudice and discrimination have been decreasing for the last decades, new forms have emerged since the 1990’s (Duckitt, 1992). Currently, prejudice is being studied not only in its explicit expression, but also in its implicit forms. This means that although people continue to have negative feelings towards other social groups, they do not necessarily express them openly due to social pressure and social desirability (Berges, 2008). In this regard, Pettigrew and Meertens (1995) developed the subtle and blatant prejudice constructs to analyze these two different forms of prejudice, being the first one an indirect and distant way, and the second one a direct and hostile expression (Ungaretti et al., 2012). On the one hand, the authors suggest that *blatant prejudice* consists of two main components: *perceived threat and rejection of the outgroup*, related to conceiving that the outgroup has a genetic inferiority; and the *opposition to intimacy with the outgroup*, in which there is an emotional rejection to have intimate contact with members of the outgroup. On the other hand, the *subtle form of prejudice* consists of the *defense of traditional values*, which means that ingroup’s values are not being respected by the outgroup; the *exaggeration of cultural differences*, which is related to the justification of the outgroup’s lower status; and the *denial of positive emotions*, which refers to not admitting explicit negative feelings towards minority groups, but revealing prejudice through the absence of any positive feelings towards the outgroup. Pettigrew and Meertens (1995) developed a scale to measure both subtle and blatant prejudice, drawing upon theoretical distinctions between these constructs. This scale has demonstrated robust psychometric properties in seven probabilistic samples from different European countries (blatant prejudice $\alpha = 0.87\text{--}0.90$; subtle prejudice $\alpha = 0.73\text{--}0.82$). Furthermore, moderate correlations were observed between the blatant and subtle prejudice subscales and the fit indices for the different theoretical models

tested through structural equations were adequate in all samples, serving as a reliable tool for assessing prejudice towards diverse social groups (Espelt et al., 2006; Frias-Navarro et al., 2009; Navas Luque et al., 2006; Pettigrew, 1997;. Moreover, it has undergone translation, adaptation, and validation for application in Spanish-speaking contexts, including Spain (Albalá Genol et al., 2022; Rueda & Navas, 1996), Chile (Cárdenas, 2006; Cárdenas et al., 2007), and Argentina (Etchezahar et al., 2022; Müller et al., 2017; Ungaretti et al., 2020).

Many studies investigated the psychosocial factors involved in blatant and subtle prejudice towards immigrants (Dhont et al., 2011; Segura-Robles et al., 2016) and established that Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) strongly predicts prejudiced attitudes (Etchezahar et al., 2022; Visintin & Rullo, 2021). The Social Dominance Theory developed by Pratto et al. (1994) holds that human societies are structured by a hierarchical system, containing dominant and dominated social groups. The dominant groups become hegemonic and are characterized by having a disproportionate amount of political power, access to material resources, and positive social image. In this sense, the authors propose three fundamental elements to explain the hierarchical system: age, gender, and a conglomerate of arbitrary intergroup characteristics, particularly important in the study of migratory movements, such as race, culture, ethnics, nationality, etc. (Sidanius & Pratto, 2004). The social inequality maintained by this dominant system is perpetuated by legitimizing myths that validate the hierarchical differences between social groups considered superior and those considered inferior. SDO is a construct created to evaluate the individual preferences that some people have, which serves the purpose of sustaining dominant attitudes toward groups perceived as inferior. For example, if migrants are perceived by natives as a subordinated and inferior group, the latter are likely to score higher on SDO than those who do not perceive the migrant community as an inferior group (Esses et al., 2001).

In addition to SDO, subtle and blatant prejudice has been studied in many countries and has been correlated with different psychosocial variables. From a sociocognitive perspective, many researchers have found that empathy not only has a significant and negative relationship with SDO (McFarland, 2010; Sidanius et al., 2013), but is also strongly correlated with the development of prejudice (Bäckström & Björklund, 2007; Boag & Carnelley, 2016). Thus, *empathic concern* has been studied as the affective component of empathy and refers to the feelings of compassion and sympathy that a person feels towards another person when they are in an unfavorable situation (Davis, 1983). Song et al. (2019) suggests that although empathy-trait is relatively stable regardless the social context, the empathy state can be malleable and developed by the induction of a specific stimulus or change in the social context. According to the study of negative attitudes towards immigrants, Miklikowska (2018) showed that empathic concern is one of the variables involved in the development of prejudice towards migrants. Moreover, some studies presented empathy as the third big predictor of generalized prejudice, after right-wing authoritarianism and

social dominance orientation (Bäckström & Björklund, 2007; McFarland, 2010). Finally, a study in Spain found that although empathy correlates negatively with both blatant and subtle prejudice, the size of the coefficients was very moderate and stronger for blatant prejudice (Álvarez-Castillo et al., 2018). Nevertheless, much research is still needed in this area to better understand the factors involved in the sociocognitive mechanisms associated with prejudice.

In addition to the previously mentioned psychosocial variables, blatant and subtle prejudice towards immigrants have been strongly correlated (López-Rodríguez et al., 2013) with the *Stereotype Content Model* (SCM) developed by Fiske et al. (2002). These authors propose that stereotypes held towards an outgroup are ambivalent, including positive and negative evaluations, not just feelings of antipathy. These authors states that the SCM has two main dimensions: *warmth*, associated with group interdependence (cooperation vs. competition); and *competence*, which refers to the evaluation of the outgroup depending on its social status. The social groups perceived as cooperative will be judged as trustworthy, friendly, and good-natured; and the outgroup perceived as competitive will be judged as cold and untrustworthy. At the same time, outgroup that are perceived as having a high social status will be judged as capable, skilful, and intelligent; while the social groups that are perceived as having a low social status will be judged as incompetent, inefficient, and unclever (Cuddy et al., 2008). In the case of prejudice against immigrants, Eckes (2002) states that the stereotype content of the migrant population in Spain is often associated with low warmth and low competence, indicating that immigrants are being attributed with limited and erroneously generalized characteristics.

Finally, Intergroup Contact Theory suggests that contact between the host population and immigrant populations improves the reduction of prejudiced attitudes toward outgroup members (Pettigrew et al., 2012). By having positive contact with some members of the outgroup, afterwards, the acceptance effects are generalized to the entire group itself (Brown & Hewstone, 2005). Moreover, many studies have shown that intergroup contact with members of one specific outgroup may reduce prejudice towards members of other outgroups not implicated in the original contact (Pettigrew, 2009). Although the direct intergroup contact is a stronger factor in reducing prejudice, indirect contact can also be a trigger for reducing blatant and subtle prejudice (Ioannou et al., 2018). This means that having a vicarious experience with the outgroup may activate positive attitudes towards its members.

The aim of the present study is to validate the SBPM scale in a Spanish sample. Subsequently, a specific objective of the study is to analyze the relationships between the two dimensions of prejudice and different psychosocial factors such as Social Dominance Orientation, Empathic Concern, Attitudes towards Maghrebis in Education, Warmth and Competence stereotypes, and Intergroup Contact. Finally, it will be analyzed whether there are significant differences in subtle and blatant prejudice against Maghrebi immigrants according to age and gender.

Method

Participants

The present study involved a non-probabilistic sample of 797 participants from Madrid (Spain). To be included in the study, participants must be at least 18 years old, have access to a stable internet connection to complete the questionnaire, and be willing to participate in online surveys. The mean age of the entire sample was 53.09 ($SD = 13.85$), 53.5% of the participants were female ($n = 426$), while 46.5% were male ($n = 371$). Regarding the educational level, 6.8% of the participants had completed primary education, 16% had completed secondary education, 20.7% had completed tertiary education, 38.8% had completed undergraduate education, and 17.7% had completed postgraduate education

Measures

Subtle and Blatant Prejudice towards Maghrebis (SBPM)

A ten-item scale, based on the original developed by Pettigrew and Meertens (1995), was adapted and validated for the purposes of this study (see also Etchezahar et al., 2022; Ungaretti et al., 2020). The scale has two dimensions, evaluating subtle prejudice (see Table 1) and blatant prejudice (see Table 1). Some of the items of the blatant prejudice dimension (2, 4, 6, and 8) have a reverse code (see Table 1). The item response format is a 5-point Likert type scale ranging from 1 = *Totally disagree* to 5 = *Totally agree*. Also, items of the blatant prejudice dimension were inverted. Higher scores on both dimensions represent higher levels of subtle and blatant prejudice.

Social Dominance Orientation (SDO)

A version of the original scale (Pratto, et al., 1994) was used, adapted and validated to the Spanish context with a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from *Strongly agree* to *Strongly disagree* (Silvan-Ferrero & Bustillos, 2007). The scale's ten items are grouped around two dimensions: Group Dominance and Opposition to Equality, which together conform the social dominance orientation construct. Higher scores address higher social dominance orientation levels. The internal consistency ($\alpha = .82$) and the construct validity (CFI = .94; RMSEA = .07) of the scale were adequate. The answer format of this scale was a 5-point Likert scale of agreement (1 = *Totally disagree*, 5 = *Totally agree*). Higher scores mean more social dominance orientation.

Empathic Concern (EC)

To evaluate this variable, the Empathic Concern (EC) dimension of the Interpersonal Reactivity Inventory (IRI; Davis, 1983) was used, validated in a Spanish speaking population by Muller et al. (2015). This dimension consists of 7 items with adequate Cronbach's Alpha index ($\alpha = .82$) and construct validity (CFI = .97; RMSEA = .01). The answer format of this scale was a 5-point Likert scale of agreement (1 = *Totally disagree*, 5 = *Totally agree*). Higher scores mean more empathic concern.

Attitudes toward Maghrebis in Education (AME)

The scale consists of seven items which linked the Maghrebis migrants with different educational scenarios. The 7 items involved the different educational levels, including cultural aspects and the State role in education. The scale shows an adequate Cronbach's Alpha index ($\alpha = .83$) and construct validity (CFI = .93; RMSEA = .02). The answer format was a 5-point Likert scale of agreement (1 = *Totally disagree*, 5 = *Totally agree*).

Intergroup Contact with Maghrebis

Participants were asked if they have had contact with Maghrebis and if so, the contact frequency. A five-point Likert-type scale was used, in which numbers mean the following: 1 = *No contact*, 2 = *Occasionally, but I do not usually talk to them*, 3 = *See them often and interact frequently*, 4 = *Have friends from that group*, and 5 = *Have relatives from that group*. Higher scores mean closer contact.

Warmth and Competence

The Stereotype Content Model (SCM; Durante et al., 2013) was used to assess the stereotypes attributed to Maghrebis. To measure attributed Warmth, the survey inquired to what extent participants evaluated Maghrebis as “warm”, “friendly”, and “good-natured”. In the case of the competent scale, it was asked to what extent were they evaluated as “competent”, “capable”, and “skilful”. All items were answered on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *Not at all* to 5 = *Extremely*). The scale shows an adequate Cronbach’s Alpha index in both dimensions ($\alpha = .81$ for Warmth and $\alpha = .86$ for Competence) and the construct validity for the bidimensional model of the scale was adequate (CFI = .97; RMSEA = .04). The answer format was a 5-point Likert scale of agreement (1 = *Totally disagree*, 5 = *Totally agree*). Higher scores for each item and both subscale’s mean more warmth and competence stereotypes.

Demographic Data

Participants were also asked about their age, gender, education, and socioeconomic level.

Procedure

Participants were recruited using social media dissemination (Facebook and Instagram) targeted by gender age, and educational level. After clicking on the post, participants were directed to an online consent form that specified the study purpose and the inclusion criteria. Furthermore, they were informed that the data derived from this research would be used only for academic and scientific purposes under the Organic Law 15/1999 on Protection of Personal Data. For the adaptation of the SBPM scale, we adhered to international methodological standards recommended by the International Test Commission (ITC) for transitioning an instrument across language contexts (Hambleton et al., 2004; Muñiz et al., 2013). We also considered the procedures used in previous adaptations for Hispanic-speaking populations (Albalá Genol et al., 2022; Cárdenas, 2010; Etchezahar et al., 2022; Müller et al., 2017; Ungaretti et al., 2020) to form a preliminary version of the scale. Following this phase, numerous items were revised or eliminated, resulting in the final 10-item scale in accordance with the recommendations of the original scale authors (Pettigrew & Meertens, 1995).

Data Analysis

A descriptive analysis was calculated of each item of the SBPM scale (means and standard deviations) and the internal consistence of each dimension was evaluated through Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient. Two models were tested (unidimensional and bidimensional) through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to examine the fit of the SBPM scale factorial structure. Different goodness-of-fit indices were utilized to establish the adjustment of the model: Chi-square (χ^2/df), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Non Normed Fit Index (NNFI), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), following Hu and Bentler’s cut off criteria (1998) ($\Delta S-B \chi^2(df) \leq 7; \leq .08$ for RMSEA; $\geq .90$ for the CFI and NNFI are indicative of adequate model fit). Criterion validity was examined by Pearson’s correlations. The scores for the correlation matrix for each dimension was formed as a sum or average of items. Descriptive statistics, correlations, and reliability analysis were conducted using the SPSS 27 software (Lizasoain & Joaristi, 2003). Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted using EQS 6.1 software (Bentler, 1995).

Results

Item Analysis and Internal Consistency of the Subtle and Blatant Prejudice towards Maghrebis (SBPM)

First, the ten items of the SBPM scale were analyzed. Final item wordings, means (*M*), standard deviations (*SD*), item-total correlations (*r_{ix}*), and Cronbach's Alpha if item deleted (*α-x*) are displayed in Table 1 for every item. The factor loadings of each item by dimension are also presented (KMO = .903; Bartlett Sphericity: *p* < .001). The first dimension was Subtle Prejudice, which explained 37.36% of the variance, and the second dimension was Blatant Prejudice, which explained 30.51% of the variance. Both dimensions explained a total of 67.88% of the variance.

Table 1
Item Analysis of the Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Towards Maghrebis (SBPM)

	M	SD	<i>r_{ix}</i>	<i>α-x</i>	1	2
Subtle prejudice (<i>α</i> = .882)						
1. En España existen otros grupos que superan el prejuicio y salen adelante por sus propios esfuerzos. Los inmigrantes magrebies deberían hacer lo mismo sin que se les tenga que dar un trato de favor. <i>Many other groups have come to Spain and overcome prejudice and worked their way up. Maghrebi immigrants should do the same without special favour.</i>	3.41	1.57	.742	.851	.822	-.201
3. Es cuestión de esfuerzo de las personas. Si los inmigrantes magrebies tan solo se esforzaran un poco más, podrían estar, al menos, tan acomodados como otros ciudadanos españoles. <i>It is just a matter of some people not trying hard enough. If Maghrebi immigrants would only try harder, they could be as well off as Spanish people.</i>	2.83	1.47	.718	.856	.808	-.172
5. Los inmigrantes magrebies enseñan a sus hijos valores y destrezas que no son adecuados para triunfar en esta sociedad. <i>Maghrebi immigrants living here teach their children values and skills different from those required to be successful in Spain.</i>	2.84	1.52	.755	.848	.797	-.262
7. Los inmigrantes magrebies son muy diferentes de los españoles en la manera en que enseñan a sus hijos a cumplir las normas. <i>Maghrebi immigrants are very different from the Spanish in the way they teach their children to follow the rules.</i>	3.14	1.48	.749	.849	.779	-.335

	M	SD	<i>r_{ix}</i>	<i>α</i> - <i>x</i>	1	2
9. Los inmigrantes magrebíes se diferencian mucho de los españoles en sus creencias y prácticas religiosas. <i>Maghrebi immigrants differ greatly from the Spanish in their religious beliefs and practices.</i> Blatant prejudice ($\alpha = .857$)	3.98	1.29	.625	.877	.748	-.088
2. No me importaría si uno de mis parientes más próximos se casara con un inmigrante magrebí, de un nivel económico parecido al mío. <i>I would not mind if a Maghrebi immigrant person who had a similar economic background as mine, joined my close family by marriage.</i>	3.80	1.40	.639	.836	-.170	.859
4. No me importaría si un inmigrante magrebí, competente en su trabajo, fuera profesor o jefe mío. <i>I would not mind if a suitably qualified Maghrebi immigrant was appointed as my professor or boss.</i>	4.35	1.22	.743	.808	-.020	.844
6. No me importaría que familiares cercanos (e.g. hijos o hermanos) tengan hijos con un inmigrante magrebí y tuviera todos los rasgos físicos de dicha persona. <i>I would not mind if close relatives (e.g. children or siblings) have children with a Maghrebi immigrant and have all the physical features of that person.</i>	3.52	1.55	.647	.835	-.239	.766
8. Estaría dispuesto/a a tener relaciones sexuales con un/a inmigrante magrebí. <i>I would be willing to have sexual relationships with a Maghrebi immigrant.</i>	3.24	1.59	.621	.841	-.287	.652
10. Los españoles e inmigrantes magrebíes nunca pueden estar realmente tranquilos unos con otros, incluso aunque sean amigos. <i>Spanish people and Maghrebi immigrants can never be really comfortable with each other, even if they are close friends.</i>	2.26	1.50	.726	.814	.159	-.576

Note. *M*: mean; *SD*: standard deviation; *r_{ix}*: item total correlation; *α*-*x*: alpha if item deleted.

In general, each item contributed to the overall scale with a relatively high correlation ($r = .62$ to $.76$), and reliability did not improve when an item was removed (Hair et al., 2006). The internal consistency of the Subtle ($\alpha = .87$ and Blatant prejudice ($\alpha = .86$) was adequate.

Validity Analysis

A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted using the maximum likelihood (ML) estimation with Satorra-Bentler’s robust correction (S-B) of the SBPM scale (Satorra, 2002). Information regarding the model fit is displayed in Table 2.

Table 2
Fit Indices for the Unidimensional and the Two-dimensional Models of the Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Towards Maghrebis (SBPM)

	S-B χ^2 (df)***	Δ S-B χ^2 (df)	NNFI	CFI	RMSEA
Unidimensional model	122.41 (35)	3.49	.897	.902	.071 [.06 – .08]
Two correlated dimensions	87.79 (34)	2.58	.958	.969	.045 [.03 – .06]

Note. χ^2 (df): Chi square (degrees of freedom); S-B χ^2 (df): Satorra-Bentler chi square (degrees of freedom); Δ S-B χ^2 (df): Division Satorra-Bentler chi square degrees of freedom; NNFI: Non Normed Fit Index; CFI: Comparative Fit Index; RMSEA: Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; Adequate fit: Δ S-B χ^2 (df) \leq 7; NNFI, CFI and IFI \geq .90; RMSEA \leq .08.

*** $p < .001$.

The results indicate that the two correlated factor model appears to be more appropriate than the unidimensional model. The fit indices for the two-dimensional model suggest that the instrument has adequate internal validity.

As suggested by the literature, the relationships between SBPM and other constructs were examined. Therefore, Pearson’s correlation coefficients were calculated for the two dimensions of the SBPM scale and SDO, Empathic Concern, Attitudes towards Maghrebis in Education, Contact, Warmth, and Competence (Table 3).

Table 3
Pearson’s Correlations Between SBPM Scale and Other Variables

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Subtle Prejudice	.88	.60**	.66**	-.39**	-.67**	-.40**	-.66**	-.59**
2. Blatant Prejudice		.86	.53**	-.32**	-.71**	-.35**	-.70**	-.58**
3. SDO			.901	-.50**	-.66**	-.29**	-.55**	-.53**
4. EC				.86	.44**	.30**	.43**	.41**
5. AME					.89	.36**	.74**	.66**
6. Contact						-	.40**	.39**
7. Warmth							.80	.75**
8. Competence								.79

Note. Cronbach’s Alpha for each scale is shown on the diagonal. SDO: Social Dominance Orientation; EC: Empathic Concern; AME: Attitudes toward Maghrebis in Education.

** $p < .01$.

As expected, results indicate a positive and significant correlation between the two dimensions of the SBPM scale and SDO, and negative with empathic concern, attitudes towards Maghrebis in education, contact, warmth, and competence. Stronger relations are observed between all variables and subtle prejudice compared to blatant prejudice, except for attitudes towards Maghrebis in education and warmth, which occurs on the contrary.

Regarding gender, measurement invariance was tested using multi-group confirmatory factor analysis (MGCFA). The following levels of invariance were examined: (1) configural invariance, testing whether the factor structure is the same across groups; (2) metric invariance, testing whether factor loadings are equal across groups; (3) scalar invariance, testing whether intercepts are

equal; and (4) residual invariance, testing whether residual variances are equal across gender (Putnick & Bornstein, 2016). Model fit was evaluated using the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). Following recommendations by Putnick and Bornstein (2016), acceptable thresholds for invariance were $\Delta CFI \leq -0.01$, $\Delta RMSEA \leq 0.015$, and $\Delta SRMR \leq 0.03$ for metric invariance, and $\Delta SRMR \leq 0.01$ for scalar and residual invariance. The configural model, which tests whether the overall factor structure is the same across gender, demonstrated good fit (CFI = 0.95, RMSEA = 0.04, SRMR = 0.05), indicating that the same factor structure is appropriate for both men and women. The metric model, which constrains factor loadings to be equal across gender, also showed acceptable fit (CFI = 0.94, RMSEA = 0.04, SRMR = 0.06), with a change in fit within acceptable limits ($\Delta CFI = -0.01$, $\Delta RMSEA = 0.001$, $\Delta SRMR = 0.01$), indicating that factor loadings are invariant across gender. The scalar model, which constrains both loadings and intercepts, showed acceptable fit (CFI = 0.93, RMSEA = 0.04, SRMR = 0.06), with changes in fit indices indicating scalar invariance ($\Delta CFI = -0.01$, $\Delta RMSEA = 0.002$, $\Delta SRMR = 0.005$). Residual invariance testing, which constrains residual variances, demonstrated acceptable fit (CFI = 0.92, RMSEA = 0.05, SRMR = 0.07), and changes in fit indices were within recommended thresholds ($\Delta CFI = -0.01$, $\Delta RMSEA = 0.003$, $\Delta SRMR = 0.01$), supporting residual invariance across gender. The results support measurement invariance across gender at all tested levels, suggesting that the scale measures the construct equivalently for both males and females. This allows for meaningful comparisons between genders and supports the generalizability of the findings across these groups (Putnick & Bornstein, 2016)

Secondly, we developed a mean comparison through *t* statistic, identifying significant statistically differences on the subtle prejudice (prejudice ($t_{(801)} = -2.042$; $p < .05$; Cohen’s $d = .25$), with men ($M = 3.43$; $SD = 1.23$) scoring higher than women ($M = 3.13$; $SD = 1.19$). Likewise, these differences were observed in the blatant prejudice dimension ($t_{(801)} = -2.742$; $p < .001$; Cohen’s $d = .22$) (Table 4), in which men ($M = 3.86$; $SD = 1.08$) scored higher than women ($M = 3.60$; $SD = 1.22$).

Table 4
Mean Differences in Subtle and Blatant Prejudice According to Gender

	Men	Women	<i>t</i> (<i>p</i>)	Cohen’s <i>d</i>
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)		
Subtle Prejudice	3.43 (1.23)	3.13 (1.19)	-2.042 ($p < .05$)	.25
Blatant Prejudice	3.86 (1.08)	3.60 (1.22)	-2.742 ($p < .001$)	.22

Note. *M* = Mean; *SD* = Standard Deviation.

Finally, no significant correlation was observed between the levels of subtle and blatant prejudice and age.

Discussion

This study aimed to validate the SBPM scale within the Spanish context, particularly focusing on attitudes towards Maghrebi immigrants. According to previous studies in different contexts (Cárdenas, 2010; Civalero et al., 2019; Martínez Sánchez & Benito-Ambrona, 2020), the two-dimension option had a more adequate fit for the assessment of prejudice than the option with only one dimension, as suggested by Prieto and Delgado (2010). The results from the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) demonstrated strong fit indexes, with the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) confirming the structural validity of the two-factor model of the scale. These findings are pivotal as they not only affirm the scale's reliability and applicability in measuring subtle and blatant forms of prejudice towards Maghrebis in Spain, but also lay a strong foundation for future research in this domain.

The significant fit indices obtained —specifically, a CFI of .969 and an RMSEA of .045— indicate an excellent fit, surpassing common acceptability thresholds. This robust validation supports the scale's use, providing researchers with a reliable tool to assess and understand prejudice dynamics more deeply. By successfully adapting and validating this scale for the Spanish population, this study allows its application in assessing prejudice towards other migrant groups within Spain, thereby enhancing the use of the scale in the Spanish context.

The results indicate that both blatant and subtle forms of prejudice are independent of each other and cannot be analyzed in a single dimension of the construct. The use of a bidimensional model of prejudice in social contexts may be a key instrument for deeper understanding of other variables related to each form of prejudice towards Maghrebi immigrants. We found reliability and validity indicators suitable for its use across our sample, providing a first approach to the subject and making further exploration of the phenomenon possible. Based on the results obtained in this study, it is possible to state that the SBPM scale has appropriate psychometric properties, including strong validity and reliability for both dimensions, as Prieto and Delgado (2010) suggested.

It is therefore possible to address the social exclusion of the Maghrebi population, where negative social representations and stereotypes of people of Maghrebi ethnicity are perpetuated, by reducing prejudicial attitudes towards them. For example, on many occasions, these stereotypes function as a trigger for attitudes opposing Maghrebi immigrants receiving social and economic aid from the Spanish State (Canto et al., 2012).

Regarding gender differences, it was found that men showed significantly higher levels of prejudice towards Maghrebis, both in the subtle and blatant dimensions. These results are consistent with previous studies in similar contexts, regardless of age: in children between 12 and 14 years old, blatant and subtle prejudice levels are higher in boys compared to girls (Song et al., 2019); as well as in the adult population, with significantly higher levels for men compared to women (Fernandez-Castillo & Fernandez, 2006). However,

although there is theoretical and empirical support for gender differences, most of it does not suggest that men should be more prejudiced than women, so it is necessary to continue to study the motivations and differential factors behind these biases (McDonald et al., 2011).

The external validity of the scale is adequate according to the psychosocial variables used to contrast the levels of subtle and blatant prejudice towards Maghrebi immigrants. As it was documented in the previous research in the study of prejudice attitudes (Dovidio et al., 2008), all the psychosocial variables used (SDO, empathic concern, warmth, competence, and intergroup contact) correlated strongly with both dimensions of the SBPM scale. In addition, the present study found that women have more blatant prejudice attitudes towards Maghrebi immigrants than men, but less subtle prejudice attitudes. This indicates that there is a tendency in men to express their prejudice towards Maghrebi immigrants in a subtle form and women in a more blatant one.

The relation between the blatant and subtle prejudice towards Maghrebi immigrants with psychosocial variables operates as the ideological background that contributes to the perpetuation of discrimination. On the one hand, the correlational results have shown that, accordingly to previous research (Álvarez Castillo et al., 2016; Passini & Morselli, 2016; Sibley & Duckitt, 2008), SDO might be operating as a psychosocial variable with a certain predictability towards the justification of social inequality, therefore showing positive relations with the prejudice towards Maghrebi.

On the other hand, as expected based on other similar studies (Albalá Genol et al., 2021; Brown & Hewstone, 2005; Froehlich & Schulte, 2019; Miklikowska, 2018), negative correlations were found between the two forms of prejudice towards immigrants and the variables: EC, AME, intergroup contact with immigrants, warmth, and competence. Regarding to EC, this variable is negatively related to both forms of prejudice, which means that people who show more empathy may have less prejudiced attitudes towards Maghrebi immigrants. Thus, the relationship between empathic concern (EC) and prejudice towards Maghrebi immigrants aligns with findings from similar research conducted by Miklikowska (2018) and Álvarez-Castillo et al. (2018). Miklikowska (2018) emphasized the significant negative correlation between EC and anti-immigrant attitudes, noting that higher levels of empathy are associated with reduced prejudice at the between-person level. This suggests that empathy operates as a potent mitigator of prejudicial attitudes, which is consistent with this study's results, where EC shows a strong negative association with both subtle and blatant forms of prejudice. Similarly, Álvarez-Castillo et al. (2018) found that the strength of these associations varied, with a more pronounced impact on subtle prejudice. This difference highlights the complexity of prejudice dynamics, where subtle forms may be more susceptible to the influences of EC, potentially due to their less blatant and more prosocial nature. The findings in the present study further suggest that, like in Álvarez-Castillo et al. (2018) and Miklikowska (2018) studies, perhaps more contextualized measures of empathy are needed to

identify cultural variations in multicultural contexts. In addition, the presence of favorable attitudes towards the presence of Maghrebis migrants in education (AME) is also negatively correlated to both forms of prejudice towards them. The correlation patterns observed in the present research not only reinforce the existing literature, but also expand on it by demonstrating these effects within the specific cultural context of Spain, which is characterized by its own unique migratory and social dynamics.

These findings should guide reflection in the field of education, which, according to Gabrielli et al. (2022), should be a space that creates less discriminatory future societies. Therefore, it will be necessary for all educational agents not to be prejudiced towards the migrant population. In this sense, intergroup contact is positioned as a key mediator in developing less blatant and subtle prejudice attitudes. Contact favors knowledge and development of empathy towards the social groups involved, dismantling certain prejudices that otherwise would be perpetuated and increased (Pettigrew & Tropp, 2008). This enables the development of greater warmth, which is positively related to EC and intergroup contact, as well as the perception of greater competence among Maghrebi immigrants.

Finally, for future investigations it is important to continue the study on the validation of the SBPM scale. Since the present study has focused on the validation of this scale, it is suggested to continue exploring the relationship between the variables studied and to obtain more detailed data on possible hierarchies and degrees of prediction between them. Furthermore, additional analysis of various psychosocial variables that may be associated with subtle and blatant prejudicial attitudes toward immigrants from diverse ethnic and cultural backgrounds in different countries and contexts is essential.

The validated scale will be instrumental in examining other psychosocial variables that may influence prejudicial attitudes toward migrants. This approach allows a better understanding of the factors driving prejudice, thereby enriching the field's theoretical foundations, and contributing to more comprehensive future studies. The alignment of these results with the study's aims reinforces the SBPM scale potential to significantly impact scholarly research, guiding subsequent inquiries into the dynamics of prejudice and social cognition within diverse populations. By providing a validated instrument, this study lays the groundwork for future research into the phenomenon of prejudice, enabling more sophisticated analyses and interventions aimed at understanding and mitigating discriminatory attitudes.

Although the study has great strengths, such as the rigorous methodological approach used to assess the psychometric properties of the scale, its limitations must also be considered. Although the sample size is robust and provides a solid basis for validating the scale, it is predominantly urban and concentrated in Madrid. This demographic focus may limit the generalizability of the results to other regions or rural areas, where social and cultural dynamics may be very different.

Conclusions

This study successfully validated the SBPM scale within the Spanish context, specifically addressing attitudes towards Maghrebi immigrants. Findings confirm that the adapted SBPM scale maintains adequate psychometric properties, demonstrating its effectiveness in capturing both subtle and blatant forms of prejudice in the Spanish population. This adaptation not only enriches the understanding of prejudice dynamics in Spain, but also serves as a crucial tool for future research aimed at studying subtle and blatant prejudices against Maghrebi in Spain. Researchers will be able to use a scale that has been specifically validated and adapted for Spanish context, ensuring that their findings are grounded in culturally relevant metrics. The study extends the application of the original framework developed by Pettigrew and Meertens (1994) into a new sociocultural landscape, offering a template for future adaptations in other regions with significant immigrant populations. Furthermore, this adaptation paves the way for adapting the scale for use in evaluating prejudice towards other migrant groups in Spain, enhancing the ability to address and understand the complexities of intergroup relations across various communities.

Finally, the scale will serve as a valuable tool for analyzing other psychosocial variables that may be moderating prejudicial attitudes toward Maghrebi and other migrant populations in Spain, facilitating a deeper understanding of the factors that influence these attitudes.

References

- Albalá Genol, M. Á., Guido, J. I., Ungaretti, J., & Rico, A. F. M. (2021). Prejuicio sutil y actitudes hacia la inclusión del profesorado y alumnado migrante magrebí. *Revista INFAD de Psicología. International Journal of Developmental and Educational Psychology*, 2(1), 127–136. <https://doi.org/10.17060/ijodaep.2021.n1.v2.2125>
- Albalá Genol, M. Á., Etchezahar, E., Guido, J. I., & Ungaretti, J. (2022). Construct validity of the attitudes towards Maghrebis in education scale (AMES). *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(12), 7303. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19127303>
- Allport, G. (1954). *The nature of prejudice*. Addison Wesley.
- Álvarez Castillo, J. L., Corpas Reina, R., & Corpas Reina, C. (2016). Predictores del prejuicio en profesionales que trabajan con colectivos en exclusión social [Predictors of Prejudice in Professionals Working with Socially Excluded Groups]. *Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 22(3), 35–50. <https://doi-org.sire.ub.edu/10.31876/rcs.v22i3.24867>
- Álvarez-Castillo, J. L., Fernández-Caminero, G., & González-González, H. (2018). Is empathy one of the Big Three? Identifying its role in a dual-process model of ideology and blatant and subtle prejudice. *PLoS One*, 13(4), e0195470. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0195470>
- Andalusian Association for Human Rights (APDHA). (2021). Human Rights on the Southern Border. APDHA. Retrieved from <https://www.apdha.org/frontera-sur-21/>
- Arancibia Martini, H., Blanco, A., Ruiz, M. A., & Castro, M. C. (2016). RIVEC (rejection, intimacy, values, emotions, and culture) prejudice scale: An adaptation to the Chilean context of the blatant and subtle prejudice scale. *Journal of Pacific Rim Psychology*, 10, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1017/prp.2016.3>

- Bäckström, M., & Björklund, F. (2007). Structural modeling of generalized prejudice: The role of social dominance, authoritarianism, and empathy. *Journal of Individual Differences*, 28(1), 10–17. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1614-0001.28.1.10>
- Bentler, P. M. (1995). EQS structural equations program manual (Vol. 6). Multivariate Software.
- Berges, B. M. (2008). Discriminación, prejuicio, estereotipos: conceptos fundamentales, historia de su estudio y el sexismo como nueva forma de prejuicio [Discrimination, Prejudice, Stereotypes: Fundamental Concepts, History of Their Study, and Sexism as a New Form of Prejudice]. *Iniciación a la Investigación*, 3, 1–16. Available at: <https://revistaselectronicas.ujaen.es/index.php/ininv/article/view/202>
- Berry, J. W., & Hou, F. (2017). Acculturation, discrimination and wellbeing among second generation of immigrants in Canada. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 61, 29–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2017.08.003>
- Boag, E. M., & Carnelley, K. B. (2016). Attachment and prejudice: The mediating role of empathy. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 55(2), 337–356. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjso.12132>
- Brown, R., & Hewstone, M. (2005). An integrative theory of intergroup contact. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 37, 255–343. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(05\)37005-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(05)37005-5)
- Bustos Martínez, L., De Santiago Ortega, P. P., Martínez Miró, M. A., & Rengifo Hidalgo, M. S. (2019). Discursos de odio: una epidemia que se propaga en la red. Estado de la cuestión sobre el racismo y la xenofobia en las redes sociales [Hate Speech: An Epidemic Spreading Online. State of the Art on Racism and Xenophobia on Social Media]. *Mediaciones Sociales*, 18, 25–42. <https://doi.org/10.5209/meso.64527>
- Canto, J. M., Perles, F., & San Martín, J. (2012). Racismo, dominancia social y atribuciones causales de la pobreza de los inmigrantes magrebíes [Racism, Social Dominance, and Causal Attributions of Poverty Among Maghrebi Immigrants]. *Boletín de Psicología*, 104, 73–86.
- Cárdenas, M. C. (2010). Forms of ethnic prejudice: assessing the dimensionality of a spanish-language version of the blatant and subtle prejudice scale. *Psicothema*, 22(1), 118–124.
- Civalero, L., Alonso, D., & Brussino, S. (2019). Evaluación del prejuicio hacia inmigrantes: adaptación argentina de la escala de prejuicio sutil y manifiesto [Assessment of Prejudice Toward Immigrants: Argentine Adaptation of the Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Scale]. *Ciencias Psicológicas*, 13(1), 119–133. <https://doi.org/10.22235/cp.v13i1.1814>
- Cuddy, A. J., Fiske, S. T., & Glick, P. (2008). Warmth and competence as universal dimensions of social perception: The stereotype content model and the BIAS map. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 40, 61–149. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(07\)00002-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(07)00002-0)
- Davis, M. H. (1983). The effects of dispositional empathy on emotional reactions and helping: A multidimensional approach. *Journal of Personality*, 51(2), 167–184. <https://doi-org.sire.ub.edu/10.1111/j.1467-6494.1983.tb00860.x>
- Dhont, K., Roets, A., & Van Hiel, A. (2011). Opening closed minds: The combined effects of intergroup contact and need for closure on prejudice. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 37(4), 514–528. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167211399101>
- Dovidio, J. F., Glick, P., & Rudman, L. A. (2008). *On the nature of prejudice: Fifty years after Allport*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Duckitt, J. H. (1992). Psychology and prejudice: A historical analysis and integrative framework. *American Psychologist*, 47(10), 1182–1193. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.47.10.1182>
- Durante, F., Fiske, S. T., Kervyn, N., Cuddy, A. J., Akande, A., Adetoun, B. E., ... & Storari, C. C. (2013). Nations' income inequality predicts ambivalence in stereotype content: How

- societies mind the gap. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 52(4), 726–746. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjso.12005>
- Eckes, T. (2002). Paternalistic and envious gender stereotypes: Testing predictions from the stereotype content model. *Sex Roles*, 47, 99–114. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1021020920715>
- Espelt, E., Javaloy, F., & Cornejo, J. M. (2006). La paradoja del racismo aversivo hacia los inmigrantes: un estudio experimental. *Revista de Psicología Social*, 21(1), 3–20. <https://doi.org/10.1174/021347406775322232>
- Esses, V. M., Dovidio, J. F., Jackson, L. M., & Armstrong, T. L. (2001). The immigration dilemma: The role of perceived group competition, ethnic prejudice, and national identity. *Journal of Social Issues*, 57(3), 389–412. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0022-4537.00220>
- Esses, V. M. (2021). Prejudice and discrimination toward immigrants. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 72, 503–531. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-080520-102803>
- Etchezahar, E., Ungaretti, J., & Marchiano, F. (2022). “Economic support? They don’t really need it”. Prejudice towards Latin American immigrants in Argentina. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 87, 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2022.01.007>
- Fernández-Castillo, A., & Fernández, J. D. (2006). Valoración del prejuicio racial en la infancia: adaptación preliminar de la escala de prejuicio racial sutil y manifiesto [Assessment of Racial Prejudice in Childhood: Preliminary Adaptation of the Subtle and Manifest Racial Prejudice Scale]. *Infancia y Aprendizaje*, 29(3), 327–342. <https://doi.org/10.1174/021037006778148033>
- Fiske, S. T., Cuddy, A. J., Glick, P., & Xu, J. (2002). A model of (often mixed) stereotype content: competence and warmth respectively follow from perceived status and competition. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 82(6), 878–902. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.82.6.878>
- Frías-Navarro, D., Monterde, H., & Peris, F. (2009). Measuring blatant and subtle prejudice. *Interpsiquis*, 1, 123–134.
- Froehlich, L., & Schulte, I. (2019). Warmth and competence stereotypes about immigrant groups in Germany. *Plos One*, 14(9), e0223103. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0223103>
- Gabrielli, S., Catalano, M. G., Maricchiolo, F., Paolini, D., & Perucchini, P. (2022). Reducing implicit prejudice towards migrants in fifth grade pupils: efficacy of a multi-faceted school-based program. *Social Psychology of Education*, 25, 425–440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-022-09688-5>
- Hambleton, R. K., Merenda, P. F., & Spielberger, C. D. (Eds.). (2004). *Adapting educational and psychological tests for cross-cultural assessment*. Psychology Press.
- Human Rights Association of Andalusia (APDHA). (2021). Human Rights on the Southern Border. APDHA. Retrieved from <https://www.apdha.org/frontera-sur-21/>
- Instituto Nacional de Estadística (2021). *Cifras de Población (CP) a 1 de enero de 2021. Estadística de Migraciones (EM). Año 2020 [Population Figures (PF) as of January 1, 2021. Migration Statistics (MS). Year 2020]*. Madrid, España. Available at: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736177000&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735573002
- Ioannou, M., Al Ramiah, A., & Hewstone, M. (2018). An experimental comparison of direct and indirect intergroup contact. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 76, 393–403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2017.11.010>
- Lizasoain, L., & Joaristi, L. (2003). *Gestión y análisis de datos con SPSS versión 11 [Data Management and Analysis with SPSS Version 11]*. Thomson.
- López-Rodríguez, L., Cuadrado, I., and Navas, M. (2013). Aplicación extendida del Modelo del Contenido de los Estereotipos (MCE) hacia tres grupos de inmigrantes en España. [Extended Application of the Stereotype Content Model (SCM) to Three Immigrant

- Groups in Spain]. *Estudios de Psicología*, 34(2), 197–208. <https://doi-org.sire.ub.edu/10.1174/021093913806751375>
- Martínez, M. F., & Martínez García, J. (2018). Procesos migratorios e intervención psicosocial [Migration Processes and Psychosocial Intervention]. *Papeles del Psicólogo*, 39(2), 96–103. <https://doi.org/10.23923/pap.psicol2018.2865>
- Martínez-Sánchez, A., & Benito-Ambrona, T. (2020). Perspectives on Africa and African immigrants: evaluation of a sample of education students (Perspectivas sobre África y los inmigrantes africanos: evaluación en una muestra de estudiantes de magisterio). *Culture and Education*, 32(4), 649–673. <https://doi-org.sire.ub.edu/10.1080/11356405.2020.1819124>
- McDonald, M. M., Navarrete, C. D., & Sidanius, J. (2011). Developing a Theory of Gendered Prejudice: An Evolutionary and Social Dominance Perspective. In *Social Cognition, Social Identity, and Intergroup Relations* (pp. 189–220). Psychology Press.
- McFarland, S. (2010). Authoritarianism, social dominance, and other roots of generalized prejudice. *Political Psychology*, 31(3), 453–477. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9221.2010.00765.x>
- Miklikowska, M. (2018). Empathy trumps prejudice: The longitudinal relation between empathy and anti-immigrant attitudes in adolescence. *Developmental Psychology*, 54(4), 703–717. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000474>
- Müller, M., Ungaretti, J., & Etchezahar, E. (2017). Argentine validation of the Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Scale towards “villeros”. *Revista de Psicología (Santiago)*, 26(1), 1–13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5354/0719-0581.2017.46204>
- Muñiz, J., Elosua, P., & Hambleton, R. K. (2013). International Test Commission Guidelines for test translation and adaptation: Second edition. *Psicothema*, 25(2), 151–157.
- Navas Luque, M., Fernández, M. C. G., Tejada, A. J. R., Fernández, P. P., & Guirado, I. C. (2006). Acculturation Attitudes and Prejudice: The Perspective of Natives and Immigrants. *Psicothema*, 18(2), 187–193.
- Palacio, J., Ramos-Vidal, I., Llinas-Solano, H., Doria-Zapata, A., & Noguera-Cadena, K. (2020). Adaptation and Validation of the Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Scale in a Colombian Sample. Available at: https://alicia.concytec.gov.pe/vufind/Record/REVPUCP_41446d465eb4fdbdb0e737e801b4112
- Passini, S., & Morselli, D. (2016). Blatant domination and subtle exclusion: The mediation of moral inclusion on the relationship between social dominance orientation and prejudice. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 89, 182–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2015.10.022>
- Pettigrew, T. F. (1997). Generalized intergroup contact effects on prejudice. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 23(2), 173–185.
- Pettigrew, T. F., & Meertens, R. W. (1995). Subtle and blatant prejudice in Western Europe. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 25(1), 57–75. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.2420250106>
- Pettigrew, T. F. (2009). Contact’s secondary transfer effect: Do intergroup contact effects spread to non-participating outgroups? *Social Psychology*, 40(2), 55–65. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167297232006>
- Pettigrew, T. F., & Tropp, L. R. (2008). How does intergroup contact reduce prejudice? Meta-analytic tests of three mediators. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 38(6), 922–934. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.504>
- Pettigrew, T. F., Tropp, L. R., Wagner, U., & Christ, O. (2012). Recent advances in intergroup contact theory. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 35(3), 271–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2011.03.001>
- Pratto, F., Sidanius, J., Stallworth, L. M., & Malle, B. F. (1994). Social dominance orientation: A personality variable predicting social and political attitudes. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 67(4), 741–763. <https://doi-org.sire.ub.edu/10.1037/0022-3514.67.4.741>

- Prieto, G., & Delgado, A. R. (2010). Fiabilidad y validez [Reliability and Validity]. *Papeles del Psicólogo*, 31(1), 67–74.
- Putnick, D. L., & Bornstein M. H. (2016). Measurement invariance conventions and reporting: The state of the art and future directions for psychological research. *Developmental Review*, 41, 71–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2016.06.004> 10.
- Rueda, J. F., & Navas, M. (1996). Towards an Assessment of New Forms of Racial Prejudice: The Subtle Attitudes of Racism. *International Journal of Social Psychology*, 11(2), 131–149. <https://doi.org/10.1174/02134749660569314>
- Satorra, A. (2002). Asymptotic robustness in multiple group linear-latent variable models. *Econometric Theory*, 18(2), 297–312.
- Segura-Robles, A., Alemany Arrebola, I., & Gallardo Vigil, M. A. (2016). Prejudiced attitudes in university students towards irregular immigrants: an exploratory study. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 14(12), 393–416. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14204/ejrep.39.15069>
- Sibley, C. G., & Duckitt, J. (2008). Personality and prejudice: A meta-analysis and theoretical review. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 12(3), 248–279. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868308319226>
- Sidanius, J., & Pratto, F. (2004). Social dominance theory: A new synthesis. In J. Jost & J. Sidanius (Eds.), *Political psychology* (pp. 315–332). Psychology Press.
- Sidanius, J., Kteily, N., Sheehy-Skeffington, J., Ho, A. K., Sibley, C., & Duriez, B. (2013). You're inferior and not worth our concern: The interface between empathy and social dominance orientation. *Journal of Personality*, 81(3), 313–323. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12008>
- Silván-Ferrero, M. D. P., & Bustillos, A. (2007). Adaptación de la Escala de Orientación a la Dominancia Social al castellano: validación de la dominancia grupal y la oposición a la igualdad como factores subyacentes [Adaptation of the Social Dominance Orientation Scale to Spanish: Validation of Group Dominance and Opposition to Equality as Underlying Factors]. *Revista de Psicología Social*, 22(1), 3–15. <https://doi.org/10.1174/0213474077796974>
- Song, Y., Nie, T., Shi, W., Zhao, X., & Yang, Y. (2019). Empathy impairment in individuals with autism spectrum conditions from a multidimensional perspective: A meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1902. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01902>
- Spanish Commission for Refugee Aid (CEAR). (2021). 2021 Report: Refugees in Spain and Europe. CEAR. Retrieved from <https://www.cear.es/informe-cear-2021/> Available at: <https://www.cear.es/informe-cear-2021/>
- Szaflarski, M., & Bauldry, S. (2019). The effects of perceived discrimination on immigrant and refugee physical and mental health. In E. Lee & N. Z. Kibria (Eds.) In *Immigration and health* (pp. 173–204). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1057-629020190000019009>
- Ungaretti, J., Etchezahar, E., & Simkin, H. (2012). El estudio del prejuicio desde una perspectiva psicológica: cuatro períodos histórico-conceptuales para la comprensión del fenómeno [The Study of Prejudice from a Psychological Perspective: Four Historical-Conceptual Periods for Understanding the Phenomenon]. *Calidad de Vida y Salud*, 5(2).
- Ungaretti, J., Etchezahar, E., & Barreiro, A. (2020). Validation of the subtle and blatant prejudice scale towards indigenous people in Argentina. *Current Psychology*, 39, 1423–1429. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-018-9844-4>
- Visintin, E. P., & Rullo, M. (2021). Humble and Kind: Cultural Humility as a Buffer of the Association between Social Dominance Orientation and Prejudice. *Societies*, 11(4), 117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc11040117>

Validacija Skale očiglednih i suptilnih predrasuda prema imigrantima iz Magreba na španskom uzorku

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Ova studija opisuje validaciju i prilagodavanje Skale suptilnih i očiglednih predrasuda (eng. Subtle and Blatant Prejudice Scale, SBPM) prema stanovnicima Magreba u španskom kontekstu i ispituje njen odnos sa drugim psihosocijalnim varijablama. Korišćen je španski uzorak od 807 učesnika iz Madrida starosti između 18 i 80 godina. Analize su obavljene korišćenjem konfirmatorne faktorske analize, uzimajući u obzir CFI, RMSEA i Pirsonov koeficijent korelacije. Eksterna validnost skale je testirana korišćenjem varijabli kao što su Orijentacija na socijalnu dominanciju (SDO), empatična zabrinutost, toplina i kompetencija i međugrupni kontakt sa stanovnicima Magreba. Rezultati su pokazali da je SBPM skala pokazala adekvatna psihometrijska svojstva. Utvrđeno je da SBPM skala pozitivno korelira sa SDO, dok je u negativnoj korelaciji sa ostalim varijablama. Stoga rezultati pokazuju da se SBPM skala može koristiti kao pouzdana mera za procenu predrasuda prema imigrantima iz zemalja Magreba u Španiji. Razmatraju se implikacije proučavanih psihosocijalnih varijabli kako bi se promovisalo smanjenje predrasuda prema imigrantima iz Magreba u španskom kontekstu.

Ključne reči: predrasude, stereotipi, orijentacija na socijalnu dominaciju, migranti, skala

RECEIVED: 07.12.2023

REVISION RECEIVED: 11.10.2024

ACCEPTED: 05.11.2024

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